

An XR eye-tracking investigation on the assessment of existing food habits

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Abstract—The work detailed in this paper is part of the development of a systematic approach to understanding human preferences and decision-making through the use of eye-tracking technology in extended reality (XR) settings. The present work aspires to better understanding of citizens’ food consumption habits, revealing the factors influencing choices and drivers that could facilitate changes in behaviour in an inclusive manner towards healthy and sustainable food consumption practices. Participants are equipped with video see-through headsets and are presented with a variety food consumption scenarios. Eye-tracking data are collected and compared against detailed questionnaires on eating habits presented directly within the XR environment. Participants’ focus on specific food options is evaluated by examining key metrics related to eye gaze such as direction, duration and frequency. The evaluation showcases the use of eye tracking to reveal preferences and biases of immersed audience that may not be captured by traditional methods focusing only on questionnaires and interviews highlighting its importance for areas such as climate change, health, nutrition and advertising that are often influenced by intangible factors. Preliminary results suggest a connection between eye gaze metrics and food selections showing influences, from socio-educational backgrounds and demonstrating the value of using XR eye-tracking for studying patterns and analyzing consumer behavior.

Index Terms—Extended Reality, Eye Tracking, Food Preferences Assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Food systems are responsible for at least 30% of the global anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions produced on an annual basis [1]. Understanding individuals’ food habits is necessary in reducing the volume of these emissions by promoting more sustainable food choices and addressing the urgency for global climate change, but also health related challenges such as obesity, malnutrition, and chronic diseases. Traditionally, food habits have been assessed using questionnaires, interviews, food diaries, surveys and large-duration clinical trials [2]. Faghih et al. [3] introduced questionnaires to correlate food habits with obesity, providing valuable insights into dietary patterns and health outcomes. However, such methods rely heavily on self-reporting [4] which can be subject to various biases and can potentially lead to data inaccuracies on actual food intake and preferences.

Questionnaires, while useful for large-scale studies, often capture minimal information related to dietary intake, missing the key reason of why individuals make certain food choices. With the advances in Extended Reality (i.e. Virtual, Aug-

mented and Mixed Reality (AR/VR/MR)), XR technologies offer a simulation environment to perform controlled experiments related to food consumption to study food choices in realistic settings. Immersive experiences allow participants to interact with virtual food items and content for the provision of detailed data on visual attention, selection processes, and consumption patterns. This approach allows for the observation of individuals’ behavior in a simulated real-life environment, offering insights into the decision-making process behind certain food choices.

Recent advances in eye-tracking technologies and the integration with XR further enhance the research capability by introducing additional objective metrics related to the individual’s visual attention, such as gaze patterns, fixation duration, and pupil dilation [5]. These metrics offer direct insights into the cognitive and emotional responses to different food stimulation, which often occurs on a subconscious level and are not easily quantified through self-reporting methods.

The approach presented in this study combines traditional questionnaire-based assessments with XR technologies and eye-tracking functionalities. By examining key metrics related to eye gaze, such as direction, duration, and frequency, individuals’ points of interests (POIs) on specific food options are evaluated within a VR setting. This approach is further enhanced by heatmaps visualizations of individuals’ attention points, to increase the existing understanding on dietary behaviors and identify the key elements necessary for the promotion of more sustainable food habits which apart from health benefits can contribute to lower GHG emissions, aligning with climate change mitigation efforts.

II. RELATED WORK

Questionnaires have been a traditional method for assessing food habits, providing insights into dietary patterns, preferences, and nutritional knowledge. Past studies have used questionnaires to understand the correlation between food habits and various health outcomes, including obesity and physical activity levels, underscoring the value of self-reported data in capturing the complexities of individual dietary behaviors [3], [6]. The development of XR technologies has introduced new assessment methods delivered through immersive experiences and eye-tracking functionalities that can simulate real-life scenarios for studying food choices and behaviors in controlled environments. Eye tracking technology in VR environments

has become a prominent area of study and commercial interest with diverse applications spanning across various fields as medicine [7], education [8], and training [9], alongside significant use in marketing and consumer behavior analysis [10]. This technology offers detailed metrics like gaze duration and frequency, pupil diameter and fixations, highlighting its versatility in both research and vast commercial settings.

Preliminary work has been carried out to explore the use of VR and eye-tracking in understanding food-related behaviors [5], indicating a potential in assessing and promoting behavioral change towards more sustainable food habits, yet direct applications in comprehensive food habits assessment are still limited [11]. Ruppenthal et al. [12] systematically reviewed eye-tracking studies on sustainable food consumption, providing a comprehensive overview of how visual attention and consumer behavior interact in the context of food choice. Furthermore, VR technology has been utilized to study the effects of immersive environments on food cravings, indicating a potential to manipulate food-related sensory cues and influence eating behavior [13]. Allman-Farinelli et al. [14] developed a VR food court to study meal choices among youth, demonstrating VR's capability to simulate real-life food environments for assessing dietary choices and behaviors. Other studies have examined the visual quality of food representations in VR, suggesting that realistic virtual food representations can impact food choice behavior of individuals [15]. Research has also extended to younger populations, where VR has been used to encourage healthy eating [16], highlighting the role of immersive technologies in forming early dietary preferences and habits. Current literature lacks in cross-validating XR technologies with traditional settings, and there is a notable gap in the use of Mixed Reality (MR) for versatile and agnostic assessment of sustainable practices, underlining a unique opportunity for further exploration. This study aims to bridge the gap in literature by combining self-reported data and eye-tracking metrics in XR environments to understand demographic preferences for food categories, offering a more interactive and realistic assessment of sustainable practices.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Background

When analyzing eye-tracking data in XR environments, it is essential to consider specific metrics like gaze direction, duration, and the number of fixations. Gaze direction provides valuable insights into participants' visual focus and attention distribution [17]. Meanwhile, the duration of gaze and the frequency of fixations offer information about the extent and frequency of participants' engagement with specific elements in the virtual space. Previous studies have emphasized the significance of these metrics in understanding visual interactions and decision-making processes [18]. Another crucial aspect of the analysis is determining the threshold for gaze duration. Extremely brief glances, such as those lasting only 0.1 seconds, may not indicate meaningful engagement or interest. In the current study we built on top of past work by setting a threshold to filter out random fixations and

concentrate on conscious visual attention [19]. Through this approach, we can differentiate between random glances and important attention points and gain a better understanding of participant interactions within the VR.

B. Description and experimental setup

The current work distinctively leverages XR hardware and the OpenXR software framework, alongside other agnostic frameworks, to perform the present validation in VR settings but facilitate seamless transition into mixed reality (MR). The method involves collecting precise measurements of participants' gaze behavior while interacting with virtual food stimuli, with the goal of understanding how visual engagement affects food choices. This approach helps collect data on gaze location, duration, and point of fixation, which can be analyzed and plotted through heatmaps to indicate areas of visual interest.

The study is divided into consecutive phases, starting with comprehensive questionnaires introduced to collect data on participant demographics, lifestyle, dietary preferences, and health issues. Following this step, participants representing specific food habit groups are exposed in an immersive VR experience where their interactions with different food images are monitored using eye-tracking technology delivered by the headsets. This setup allows for gathering quantitative insights into participants' visual attention patterns for different food choices and correlating this with self-reported preferences.

Eye-tracking metrics such as fixation duration, frequency, and fixation point are collected and analyzed. The data are further improved by converting quaternion rotation data into Euler coordinates to allow precise analysis of gaze direction and focus. The use of quaternions ensures accuracy in representing 3D rotational motion, which is crucial for identifying specific areas in a VR environment that capture the participant's attention. The ultimate goal is to reveal and understand the psychological processes behind unconscious preferences and food choice decisions. OVR eye gaze functions at the hardware level by using infrared sensors and cameras integrated into the VR headset to track the reflection of the Infrared (IR) light off the user's pupils, allowing for precise determination of gaze direction and fixation points. The experimental flowchart detailing these phases and methodologies is illustrated in Fig. 1, providing a visual representation of the study's comprehensive and innovative approach to exploring the intricate dynamics between visual attention and dietary decision-making. The scenario is selected to facilitate the deployment of a proof-of-concept focused on various food options aiming to assess the unbiased food preferences of the participants.

C. Definition of Scenarios

The definition of the scenarios in an immersive setup involves several steps, including the design of the virtual environment, the selection and placement of the available options as well as the selection of the most appropriate environment to perform the assessment. For the purposes of the present study, aiming the definition of a functional prototype able

Fig. 1. Virtual Reality-Based Behavioral Analysis Flowchart: Identifying Dietary Choices through Eye-Tracking, HeatMaps, and Data Analysis

to drive some initial conclusions on the factors influencing food choices and supporting agnostic frameworks that are transferable in other settings, we proceeded with a simplistic foundational scenario in VR. Photos of different food items were placed against a wall in a virtual room and eye tracking data were collected. This foundational phase is necessary to ensure that the current agnostic methodology and technology is validated and tested before shifting into AR scenarios that are more complex and challenging at once.

D. Eye-Tracking Data Collection and Analysis

The Unity development environment incorporates the OVR Eye Gaze component that Oculus has developed into a game object that represents the user's eyes. This component is responsible for tracking either the left or right eye with the help of a camera located on the Quest headset and detecting position and rotation data. As a result, an object from which we retrieve OVR Eye Gaze data Fig. 2 shows us the true movement and orientation of the human eye.

Following the generation of the eye rotation data, a custom script is implemented to direct a ray from the focal point of an animated eye (game object) Fig. 3 towards a specific direction, at a given frequency (e.g., 50 Hz). The resulting ray-casting outcomes are then analyzed to identify interactions between objects within the virtual environment. Once the ray intercepts the object that is considered of interest (e.g., an image of a food item) and remains focused for more than a certain level, such as 0.15 seconds, the timer will begin recording the event. A collection of 3D points is preserved to keep track of where a ray hits an object, regardless of the type. The coordinates (x, y, z), the timestamp of the collision, and the name of the object involved are entered into a list. By collecting such data, an analysis after processing is carried out to study user gaze behavior in the virtual world down to detail.

Fig. 2. Sensors setup, avatar testing and calibration

Fig. 3. VR environment initial calibration of game objects

E. Analysis of Experimental Visual Attention and Self-Reporting Data

The analysis of the experiment lies at visual attention data, which is collected from eye-tracking metrics in VR. This data is then matched with self-reported questionnaires to identify the individuals' trends and preferences related to their food choices. In addition, the analysis produces two-dimensional heatmaps to capture and depict the data gathered from eye tracking. These heatmaps are able to effectively emphasize the parts of the VR environment that receive the most attention, thus helping to highlight where people's main interest lies and where their primary engagement originates. Also, by overlaying these points of attention on a background of food items, researchers can determine which ones attract the highest visual focus, thus inferring higher levels of interest or preference.

On the basis of this visual attention information and the self-reports from questionnaires, it can be determined that it is possible to study food habits in a more subjective manner, relying on quantitative rather than qualitative metrics. The questionnaires collect structured and detailed information, including diet restrictions, health, ethical issues, cultural impact, and personal preferences. By comparing the explicit preferences and inclinations in the questionnaires to the implicit interest in the VR environment, we are able to identify the drivers of food selection behaviors.

IV. RESULTS

A. Assessment of Participants

A comprehensive data collection process was carried out with 114 participants recruited for the study. The process commenced with an extensive questionnaire and several key factors influencing the food choices of participants were evaluated. Taste emerged as the primary factor, followed by health, cost, and convenience whereas ingredient freshness, allergies, traditions, and environmental impact were also considered Fig. 4. In addition, the analysis shows a higher proportion

Fig. 4. Key Factors affecting food habits of dietary groups

of overweight in the carnivorous group than their vegetarian and vegan counterparts. In this case, statistical analysis is supported by various research works, which often refer to plant-based diets as factors that promote lower body mass indices (BMIs) and better health outcomes [20]. Table I provides a brief overview of food choices of diverse demographic clusters among respondents. The assessment via the traditional questionnaires showed a diversity of food preferences as indented during the design phase of the experiments. This diversity reveals the complexity of behavior patterns associated with food choice and highlights the need for a wide range of dietary practices to be considered in such studies. The most noticeable differences are found between carnivores, vegetarians, and vegans in terms of gender distribution, body mass index (BMI) classifications, health concerns and environmental impact considerations. Table I shows that the proportions of males are higher among respondents practicing a carnivorous

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF DIETARY GROUPS ACROSS VARIOUS CATEGORIES

Category	Vegetarians	Omnivorous	Carnivorous
Age Groups			
18-24	28.57%	6.25%	0%
25-34	14.29%	23.96%	14.29%
35-44	28.57%	56.25%	57.14%
45-54	0%	7.29%	0%
55-64	0%	3.13%	14.29%
65+	28.57%	3.13%	14.29%
Gender			
Male	28.57%	37.5%	71.43%
Female	71.43%	60.42%	28.57%
Non-binary	0%	2.08%	0%
Prefer not to say	0%	2.08%	0%
BMI			
Underweight	0%	2.08%	0%
Normal Weight	57.14%	63.54%	28.57%
Overweight	42.86%	28.13%	71.43%
Obese	0%	6.25%	0%
Environmental Impact			
Very Low	0%	13.54%	14.29%
Low	0%	17.71%	28.57%
Moderate	42.86%	46.88%	42.86%
High	42.86%	19.79%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	2.08%	0%
Health Concerns			
Very Low	0%	4.12%	0%
Low	0%	7.22%	42.86%
Moderate	57.14%	38.14%	42.86%
High	28.57%	42.27%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	8.25%	0%
Ethical Concerns			
Yes	71.43%	27.08%	0%
No	28.57%	72.92%	100%

diet but lower for those practicing vegetarian or vegan diets, implying probable sex-related inclinations and cultural factors influencing the dietary preferences.

B. XR demonstration

After the completion of the initial questionnaire, three participants representing the main dietary groups found within the study-vegetarian, carnivorous, and others were selected to further explore the VR environment. Table II presents eye-tracking data results for the three individuals for the three different food scenarios. These individuals were carefully chosen to represent the main dietary groups to ensure a focused and initial exploration of dietary preferences in VR. Future work will present 3D models of food options in MR environments and include a larger number of participants to analyze statistical variances among dietary groups. The analysis indicates that vegetarians exhibited a pronounced preference for sustainable food scenarios, particularly those showcasing vegetables, aligning with their dietary ethics and environmental consciousness. Conversely, individuals identifying as carnivorous demonstrated a stronger interest in meat-based food scenarios, often associated with less sustainable choices. This trend was similarly observed among participants with no specific dietary restrictions, who showed interest in a broader range of food scenarios, including those less sustainable. These findings underscore the complex relationship

TABLE II

RESULTS OF COUNT, TOTAL, MAX, AND AVERAGE GAZE DURATION PER FOOD SCENARIO AT A SAMPLING RATIO OF $f = 50$ HZ AND MINIMUM GAZE FIXATION > 0.15 S

Group	Scenario	Count	Total Gaze (s)	Avg (s)	Max (s)
Vegetarian	Fish	13	9.59	0.74	2.44
	Pasta	14	10.56	0.75	1.68
	Pizza	15	10.06	0.67	2.44
	Steak	8	3.48	0.44	0.74
	Fruits	11	10.34	0.94	0.74
	Salad	18	16.17	0.9	2.34
Omnivorous	Fish	10	4.00	0.40	0.88
	Pasta	2	1.08	0.54	0.58
	Pizza	8	4.12	0.52	1.04
	Steak	11	11.96	1.087	3.32
	Fruits	7	4.58	0.65	1.88
	Salad	3	2.02	0.67	0.90
Carnivorous	Fish	5	1.94	0.39	0.78
	Pasta	13	13.28	1.02	4.48
	Pizza	12	24.84	2.07	9.50
	Steak	5	12.48	2.50	6.28
	Fruits	6	3.96	0.66	1.34
	Salad	3	2.22	0.74	1.56

between dietary preferences and environmental sustainability considerations. Future research will include more participants and focus on identifying which food scenarios are associated with the maximum gaze duration, exploring potential correlations between dietary preferences and visual engagement. This will potentially provide insights into the benefits of producing sustainable food that resembles non-sustainable food in appearance. Fig. 5 presents Heatmaps results normalized by a logarithmic transformation in the case of a Carnivorous participant, highlighting increased attention points for steak and pizza compared to the other more sustainable food consumption scenarios provided. The logarithmic transformation is used to reduce the skewness of the data, enhancing visibility and contrast in the heatmap, especially when the range of gaze counts varies widely. In order to better understand the visual attention points, heatmaps were generated directly within the XR environment for an omnivorous participant, highlighting the specific areas where visual attention was most concentrated Fig. 6. One of the key elements of the present study was the setting of virtual reality scenarios to enable participants to interact with a multitude of food options with diverse dietary content and similarly categorized into groups during the questionnaire stage. To ensure the accuracy of this immersive experience, eye-tracking technology embedded within the VR setup was employed to measure participants' levels of visual engagement towards these food items. The examination of eye-tracking data helped to clearly demonstrate individual profiles and visual biases towards particular categories and ingredients, allowing further consideration of self-reported eating behavior as related to what people actually perceive in the XR world. A key finding was the ability to grasp the subtleties of food preferences, as it helped make the observation of the immediate reactions beyond people's self-reported preferences and beliefs. These comprehensive results reveal

Fig. 5. Top: Heatmaps for Carnivorous Participant. Bottom: Game View Interaction Points.

Fig. 6. Visual attention heatmaps generated within the VR environment for carnivorous participant.

an eclectic tapestry of influences contributing to food choices in individuals from diverse demographic backgrounds as they include both subjective self-report data and objective visual attention metrics. Future research will build on these findings by incorporating heatmaps directly in the MR environment to compare attention points of individuals and assess engagement

levels in VR and MR environments. Additionally, the research will identify the key drivers that different dietary groups focus on among health, environmental, and accessibility factors. This will inform where marketing and advertising of food should be focused in order to create engaging content that can trigger behavioral change. This approach not only broadens the understanding of how individuals interact with virtual food environments but also enhances the potential for targeted nutritional interventions.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The assessment within the virtual environment, focusing on various aspects of food habits, revealed a notable trend among individuals with sustainable dietary preferences. These users consistently exhibited extended gaze duration on images of sustainable food options, indicating a stronger interest or preference compared to those with less sustainable habits. However, it was also observed that the attention given to unsustainable food choices by this group remained significant, highlighting a nuanced interaction between proclaimed food preferences and actual visual engagement. But to proceed to more concrete conclusions, further investigation of other qualitative metrics need to be performed to capture virtual engagement (such as selection patterns), along with physiological response (such as changes in pupil dilation and heart rate). This underscores the potential for extended reality assessments to contribute to positive changes in individual behavior towards healthy and sustainable food consumption as a result of a sustainable food system transformation. This contrast was more pronounced when compared to the gaze patterns of individuals with carnivorous preferences towards sustainable food items, suggesting underlying complexities in dietary choices and visual attraction in virtual settings. Future research will extend these observations into XR (mixed and augmented reality) environments, blending the physical surroundings with immersive content incorporating pupil dilation metrics to uncover deeper insights into the cognitive and emotional factors driving these visual attention patterns in dietary choices. Extended Reality aims to immerse the participants into more realistic settings to elicit genuine behaviour. Additional scenarios will span against a variety of consumer and customer choices and habits (such as, circular economy and climate resilience) and metrics will be collected on how targeted campaigns may promote a paradigm shift towards more sustainable practices. Increased insights into how small-scale actions will contribute to societal acceptance and a positive shift in sustainable habits through better understanding of which actions and ultimately policies are more effective.

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